

Prevalence of Aflatoxins in Commonly Consumed Foods in Western Kenya

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ABSTRACT

Aflatoxins are secondary fungal metabolites that contaminate cereals, groundnuts and animal source foods and are a recognized health risk. Contamination of staple foods in Kenya has in the past resulted into loss of lives and condemnation of large quantities of food, contributing to food insecurity. Data on prevalence of aflatoxin contamination of sorghum, millet, groundnut and maize in Bungoma, Busia and Kakamega Counties are limited. This study investigated the occurrence of total aflatoxins in maize, maize flour, finger millet and sorghum from Bungoma, Busia and Kakamega Counties of

western Kenya. Forty (40) groundnut samples, 16 finger millet, 19 sorghum, 47 maize and 33 maize flour samples were collected from households for analysis of aflatoxins. The samples were analysed for total aflatoxins using an ELISA based Reveal Q+ kit. Overall, all groundnut samples, 81% of finger millet, 95% of sorghum, 57% of maize and 85% of maize flour samples were positive for aflatoxins. Of these, the proportion of samples with aflatoxin levels above the Kenya Bureau of Standards limit of 10 µg/kg were 15% for groundnut, 13% for finger millet, 11% for sorghum, 22% for maize and 77% for maize flour. The various aflatoxin levels in groundnut, sorghum, maize and maize flour were not significantly different ($p>0.05$) across the counties. However, for finger millet, the various levels of aflatoxins significantly varied across the counties ($p=0.047$), with Busia county having significantly more samples with aflatoxin concentration below 10 µg/kg compared to Bungoma and Kakamega. The study shows that the commonly consumed foods in the study areas are contaminated with aflatoxins but the severity of contamination varies across the food types. There is need for interventions for controlling aflatoxins in the foods to reduce household dietary exposure. This is critical as the food products made from maize, finger millet, sorghum and groundnuts are consumed by vulnerable population groups (children and the elderly).

INTRODUCTION

Aflatoxins are a group of highly poisonous compounds produced in a variety of substrates by fungi of the species *Aspergillus flavus* and *A. parasiticus*. They affect over 25% of the world's global food supply (Eskola *et al.*, 2020). Specifically, aflatoxins pose a serious threat in foods like maize, nuts, oil crops and dried fruit, where high temperatures and humid conditions favour their growth and food spoilage. There are four main aflatoxins commonly encountered in foods and feeds namely: aflatoxin B1 (AFB1), aflatoxin B2 (AFB2), aflatoxin G1 (AFG1) and aflatoxin G2 (AFG2). Aflatoxin M1 (AFM1) and aflatoxin M2 (AFM2) are metabolites of AFB1 and AFB2, respectively, that can occur in milk and milk products from animals and humans consuming feeds and foods contaminated with the B aflatoxins (Iqbal *et al.*, 2013).

Ingestion of aflatoxins is the primary source of exposure for humans and animals, and this causes aflatoxin poisoning (aflatoxicosis). The worst outbreak of aflatoxin poisoning in the world was reported in Kenya (Omara *et al.*, 2021). The largest outbreak due to maize aflatoxin poisoning was reported in 2004 where 125 people died out of the 317 reported cases (Lewis *et al.*, 2005). This has triggered campaigns regarding aflatoxin contamination in maize in Kenya. However, there is need to highlight chronic incidences of aflatoxin poisoning from other commonly consumed foods in the country, including finger millet, sorghum and groundnut. Data on prevalence of aflatoxin contamination of sorghum, millet, groundnut and maize in Bungoma, Busia and Kakamega Counties are scanty. Previous studies have investigated prevalence of aflatoxins in dietary staples in Busia (Awuor *et al.*, 2020) and in cereals in Nandi (Sirma *et al.*, 2015). Data on the prevalence of aflatoxins in commonly consumed foods are essential to understand their impact on health and to develop effective mitigation strategies. The current study determined the occurrence of total aflatoxins in finger millet, sorghum, groundnut and maize in Bungoma, Busia and Kakamega Counties of Western Kenya. Region-specific data enables the identification of susceptible foods that are responsible for exposure to toxins in specific populations (Awuor *et al.*, 2020).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection

A total of 155 food samples comprising of groundnut (n=40), finger millet (n=16), sorghum (n=19), maize grains (n=47) and maize flour (n=33) were collected from households in Bungoma, Busia and Kakamega Counties for analysis of aflatoxin contamination (Table 1). Each sample weighed approximately 250-500g. The samples were collected in brown paper bags. For samples in the storage containers, a sub-sample was drawn from the top, middle and bottom of the storage containers, mixed together and collected in the brown sampling bag. The samples were transported in boxes to the laboratory and stored at 4°C in a cold room. Aflatoxin analysis was carried

out at the Regional Mycotoxin Research Laboratory at the Kenya Agricultural & Livestock Research Organization (KALRO) in Katumani.

Table 1: Food samples collected for mycotoxin analysis in Western Kenya

County	Sub-county	Ward	Number of food samples collected				
			Groundnut	Finger millet	Sorghum	Maize	Maize flour
Bungoma	Bumula	Mateka	11	2	5	15	15
Busia	Nambale	Bukhayo East	14	11	6	15	3
Kakamega	Mumias West	Musanda	15	3	8	17	15
Total			40	16	19	47	22

Aflatoxin analysis

Samples received in grain form were finely ground in a Kenwood Kitchen blender. After thorough mixing of ground samples, one 20 g sub-sample of each sample was weighed and analyzed for aflatoxin using an-ELISA based Reveal Q+ kit following manufacturer's instructions. The kit has a lower and upper detection limit of 2.0 and 150 µg/kg, respectively. In brief, the samples were extracted with 65% ethanol by shaking at 200 rpm for three minutes on an orbital shaker (HS501 IKA-WERKE, Germany). After settling for a few minutes, the supernatant was filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The extract was mixed with sample diluent provided in the kit and a Reveal Q+ lateral flow strip was inserted in sample cup containing 100 µl of the mixture. The strip was left to process for 6 minutes, after which it was inserted in a sample cartridge. The cartridge was inserted in the AccuScan Gold reader and aflatoxin levels were quantified in micrograms per kilogram (µg/kg). Samples with aflatoxin levels above 150 µg/kg were serially diluted, retested and dilution factor considered during interpretation of results. The aflatoxin levels for the sample were compared with the levels in aflatoxin reference material of known concentration ((6.1+/- 2.2 µg/kg) for validation.

Data analysis

The data were summarized using MS-Excel. To compare proportions of aflatoxin contamination of the various foods amongst the counties, chi-square and Fisher's exact test were used. Significance was reported at 95% confidence interval ($p \leq 0.05$). Statistical analysis was done in Genstat® for Windows™. 15th Edition (Payne *et al.*, 2012).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Aflatoxin levels in the food samples

Overall, 88% of the samples were contaminated with aflatoxin levels, ranging from 2.1 to 381 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ (Table 2). This indicates pervasive contamination of the dietary staples in the three counties during the time of this study. Twelve percent (12%) of the samples had no detectable aflatoxins ($< 2 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), 70% were contaminated with aflatoxin levels within KEBS regulatory threshold of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, and 18% had aflatoxin levels above 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ (Table 2). The fact that 88% of all the samples were contaminated with aflatoxins indicates dietary aflatoxin exposure for consumers. The fact that 70% of all the samples had aflatoxin levels within the KEBS limit could be preventive against acute aflatoxicosis. However, consumers are still at risk of chronic exposure. This indicates that consumers in the three counties are chronically exposed to aflatoxins through their dietary staple. Dietary exposure to aflatoxins is a public health concern, as epidemiological studies have shown association between cancer incidence and aflatoxin content of the diet (Kimanya *et al.*, 2021; Chen *et al.*, 2022). Ingestion of low to moderate levels of aflatoxins have been associated with stunting in children (Hoffmann *et al.*, 2021; Kang'ethe *et al.*, 2017; Rasheed *et al.*, 2014).

Table 2: Aflatoxin levels ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) in groundnut, finger millet, sorghum, maize and maize flour from various parts of Western Kenya

Food sample	County	n	Number of samples with the specified aflatoxin concentration			Range of positive samples ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	Mean of positive samples ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)
			< 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$	< 2-10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$	>10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$		
Groundnut	Bungoma	11	0	9	2	2.6-25.1	6.8
	Busia	14	0	13	1	2.7-12.2	5.1
	Kakamega	15	0	12	3	2.2-85.3	11.0
Finger millet	Bungoma	2	1	1	0	2.1-2.1	2.1
	Busia	11	2	9	0	2.2-6.1	3.1
	Kakamega	3	0	1	2	5.2-188.0	80.7
Sorghum	Bungoma	5	0	5	0	3.3-8.6	5.7
	Busia	6	1	5	0	3.9-8.9	6.1
	Kakamega	8	0	6	2	4.1-42.5	12.2
Maize	Bungoma	16	3	9	4	2.2-132.4	23.6
	Busia	15	2	11	2	2.4-23.2	6.6
	Kakamega	15	4	9	4	2.1-381	57.4
Maize flour	Bungoma	15	2	8	5	3-53.4	13.0
	Busia	3	0	3	0	3.6-4.2	3.8
	Kakamega	15	3	8	4	2.7-54.7	12.5

Overall, all groundnut samples, 81% of finger millet, 95% of sorghum, 57% of maize and 85% of maize flour samples were positive for aflatoxins. Of these, the proportion of samples with aflatoxin levels above the Kenya Bureau of Standards limit of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ were 15% for groundnut, 13% for finger millet, 11% for sorghum, 22% for maize and 77% for maize flour. Findings in the present study show higher values for aflatoxins than those reported by Sirma *et al.* (2015) who found that 60% of household cereal samples were positive for aflatoxins with a range of 0.17-5.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. Aflatoxin contamination varied across the food types. Aflatoxin levels in finger millet, sorghum, groundnut and maize ranged from 2.1-188 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, 3.3-42.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, 2.6-85.35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and 2.1-381 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, respectively. These values are higher than those reported by Sirma *et al.* (2015) who reported values of 0.1-210

$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, 0.1-6.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and 0.1-5.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, respectively. The values are also higher than those reported by Awuor *et al.*, (2020) for maize, finger millet, sorghum and groundnuts in Busia. The high aflatoxin contamination of groundnut and cereals could have been due to poor postharvest techniques and the environmental pre-disposing factors (high temperatures and relative humidity).

Proportion of positive samples above Kenya Bureau of Standards limit of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$

Overall, the proportion of positive samples with aflatoxin levels above the Kenya Bureau of Standards limit of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ were 15% for groundnut, 13% for finger millet, 11% for sorghum, 22% for maize and 77% for maize flour (Figure 1). These findings are consistent with the findings of Awuor *et al.* (2020).

Figure 1: Percentage of samples with aflatoxin levels more than 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ per food sample in the various counties

Association between aflatoxin levels and food samples across counties

The various aflatoxin levels in groundnut, sorghum, maize and maize flour were not significantly different ($p>0.05$). However, for finger millet, the various levels of aflatoxins significantly varied across the counties ($p=0.067$), with Busia county having significantly more samples with aflatoxin concentration 2-10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ compared to Bungoma and Kakamega (Table 3).

Table 3: Fisher's Exact Test for association between aflatoxin levels and food samples across counties

Food sample	County	Number of samples with the specified aflatoxin concentration			<i>p</i> -value
		< 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$	2-10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$	>10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$	
Groundnut	Bungoma	0	9	2	0.632
	Busia	0	13	1	
	Kakamega	1	11	3	
Finger millet	Bungoma	1	1	0	0.047*
	Busia	2	9	0	
	Kakamega	0	1	2	
Sorghum	Bungoma	0	4	0	0.438
	Busia	1	5	0	
	Kakamega	0	6	2	
Maize	Bungoma	3	9	4	0.828
	Busia	2	11	2	
	Kakamega	4	9	4	
Maize flour	Bungoma	2	8	5	0.828
	Busia	0	3	0	
	Kakamega	3	8	4	

*Significant at $p\leq 0.05$

CONCLUSION

This study gives an outlook of aflatoxin contamination in commonly consumed foods in Bungoma, Busia and Kakamega Counties of western Kenya. The study shows that the commonly consumed foods in the study areas are contaminated with aflatoxins but the severity of contamination varies across the food types. Maize was most contaminated with about a quarter of maize grains and three-

quarters of household maize flour having levels above Kenya's regulatory limit. There is need for interventions for controlling aflatoxins in the foods to reduce household dietary exposure. This is critical as the food products made from maize, finger millet, sorghum and groundnuts are consumed by vulnerable population groups including children and the elderly.

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